

Report on International Open Data Day Nairobi 2019

IODD is an annual celebration of open data all over the world and March 2nd, 2019 was the 9th time in history where various groups create events on the day and in Kenya it was no exception. The event was attended by graduate students from various universities, industry experts and representatives from academia. Two confirmed speakers sent a last minute cancellation and could not be replaced in time.

Event speakers

Allan Ochola and Janegrace Kinyanjui

The topics discussed during the event are the role of libraries in promoting open access/ open data which was highlighted by Janegrace Kinyanjui, University librarian, Egerton University and Allan Ochola, graduate student, Kenyatta University presented on opportunities available in open data and how to practice open data. The unique nature of the event enabled participants from various interdisciplinary backgrounds to define strategies that advance open data globally and locally, learn about recent advances in open data.

Discussions

The format of the event allowed for peer discussions from the participants. From the audience discussions on sources of open data, data interoperability, data timeliness, data ownership, data privacy and confidentiality, incentives for sharing data including a revival of the Kenya Open Data Initiative (KODI) took place during the event. Other notable discussions that happened include why many open data initiatives are driven to open government data. But arguably, people also own as much data held by private sector actors who are increasingly locking away what they and many consider to be ‘their’ data.

Future directions

Notwithstanding, there is a lot of interest in creating an environment that facilitates effective sharing and re-use. Participants’ feedback reveals that there is little in the way of open data among the public due to the lack of an open culture and processes that are not user responsive. Not surprisingly, key data sets to support the open data evangelism (e.g. data on cancer and maternal mortality) are largely absent as open data.

Therefore, there is a need:

- To develop and organize training workshops for open advocates.
- Promote exchange of ideas among different stakeholders.
- Establish connectivity of open advocates and strategic partners
- Open landscape in Kenyan Universities: awareness creation and infrastructure development

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